

From Natural Gas to Hydrogen

Industrial Oxy-combustion Through
Combined Experimental Trials
& CFD simulations

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Combustion at Air Liquide

Oxy-Fuel Combustion Developments for more than 50 Years

Energy-intensive industries processes

H₂/CO
production

Non-ferrous
(Cu, Al, Pb...)

Steel

Cement

Energy

Glass

Drivers

- Energy efficiency
- Reduction of CO₂ emissions
- Reduction of pollutant emissions (NO_x)

Technologies

- Oxy-fuel combustion
- Heat recovery / Reactants preheating
- H₂ combustion

PRECIZE Project

7 years (2024 - 2030)

PRocédé ECologique et Innovant de liants de spécialité Zéro Emission

Current situation

Sustainable transformation

Tomorrow with PRECIZE

Project main objective

Decarbonize calcium aluminate production using hydrogen oxy-combustion

One of Air Liquide's objectives

Provide flexible burners in order to qualify the new calcium aluminate melting process of Imerys using H₂/O₂ combustion

Context

Main Challenges for H₂ Combustion

Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Risk of leakage, High reactivity...
Burner Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Control of NOx emissions■ Control of flame length■ Control of heat transfer profile
Impacts on the Process	<p>→ <i>high partial pressure steam in the flue gases</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Product quality■ Attack of furnace refractories■ Radiation from the flame & energy efficiency
Economics & CO ₂	<ul style="list-style-type: none">■ Cost of hydrogen vs expected CO₂ emissions reduction and alternative decarbonation strategies■ H₂ production and availability

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Today's Focus

Objectives

Evaluate the impact of transitioning from NG/O₂ to H₂/O₂ combustion

- **Characterize burner performance** in an Air Liquide R&D pilot by assessing
 - Flame length and stability
 - Heat transfer to the load
 - Flue gas emissions
- **Conduct RANS simulations**

De-risk and validate burner readiness ahead of industrial trials at the Imerys innovative furnace site

AGENDA

Context & Objectives

Experimental Framework
Pilot & Operating conditions

Experimental Results
Effect of NG substitution with H₂

CFD Simulations
NG / O₂ case

Concluding Remarks

Experimental Framework

One of Air Liquide R&D Pilots...

■ Unique Facility - High Flexibility

- Test burners for various customer processes
- Up to 2 MW
- Up to 1600°C

■ Advanced Instrumentation

- Flame imaging
- Heat transfer profiles
- Flue gases analyses + in-situ gas analyses

■ 24/7 operation without human supervision

Experimental Framework

Characteristics

Dual-flame burner

Pile mounted inside R&D pilot to meet Imerys conditions

- No melting phase

Operating conditions tested

- Neat NG & H₂
- NG / H₂ blends on power basis
 - 25%, 50% & 75%

Measurements

- Flame imaging
 - Direct visualisation
 - OH* radical chemiluminescence (intensified camera + UV lens + 310 nm bandpass filter)
- Crown temperature & Heat transfer
- Flue gas analysis (dry and wet basis)

Experimental Results

Direct Flame Visualization - NG / O₂

Total burner thermal input 800 kW:

Upper Lance 300 kW | Lower Lance 500 kW

High momentum

Low momentum

Flames are attached to the burner nozzles & no hot spots observed on the burner block

Experimental Results

Flame Visualization using OH* Radical Chemiluminescence

High momentum

Low momentum

- OH* radicals are known to be good markers of the flame reaction zone. This technique is used to determine the flame length
- OH* images were successfully captured for all operating conditions
- It was not possible to completely capture tilted flames because of the limited optical accessibility

Experimental Results

Flame Visualization using OH* Radical Chemiluminescence

- 50 instantaneous images captured were averaged to minimize random noise. The flame contour was extracted using the classical Otsu* technique
- The substitution of NG with H₂ results in a decreased flame length by approx. 20%, when comparing pure NG and H₂ cases
- The flame length further decreases by approx. 14% while increasing the fuel jet momentum

*Otsu's method is a technique that automatically calculates the optimal threshold to isolate the flame from the background as clearly as possible, without manual adjustment

Experimental Results

NG vs H₂ - Temperature along the crown & at the chimney

NG substitution with H₂ - High Momentum

Slight drop in crown and stack temperatures during the transition from NG to H₂

Experimental Results

NG vs H₂ - Heat transfer to the load

NG substitution with H₂ - High Momentum

Energy transferred to the load is similar when replacing NG with H₂

Experimental Results

FG composition & NO_x emissions

Non-monotonic NO_x trend under progressive H₂ replacement

CFD Simulations

Geometry & Mesh generation

Grid mesh generation

- 1.8 millions polyhedral cells
- Criteria:
 - Skewness of 0.011
 - Orthogonal quality of 0.96

CFD Simulations

Physical Models & Operating condition

Physical Models

- **Combustion** → Non-premixed (Chemical equilibrium)
- **Radiation** → **Discrete Ordinates**
 - *WSGG model (4 gray gases) with fitted coefficients for CH_4/O_2*
 - *New set of coefficients for H_2 combustion (and any mixture $\text{CH}_4/\text{H}_2/\text{O}_2$)*
- **Turbulence** → Realizable k - ϵ
- **NO_x Emissions** → Partial-equilibrium
 - *Fluent post-processor model is used*
 - *Extended Zel'dovich model*

 For oxy-combustion, thermal NO_x formation is predominant

Operating condition

- NG/O_2 at 800 kW: *Upper flame* → 300 kW & *Lower flame* → 500 kW

CFD Simulations

Temperature field

300 kW
+
500 kW

Thermal Power 800 kW

- 2D temperature contour at the vertical mid plane & stoichiometric mean mixture fraction represented by white lines

CFD Simulations

Temperature Field along the pile

Simulation

Experiment
(using infrared borescope)

CFD Simulations

Temperature Profiles: Comparison with Experiments

Symbols and dashed lines represent experiments and simulations, respectively

Satisfactory agreement is obtained between experiments and predicted temperatures ahead of the pile

Concluding Remarks

- **Experimental trials conducted in one of Air Liquide's R&D pilot to assess the impact of switching from NG → H₂**
 - No hot spots observed when switching from NG to H₂
 - Flame length decreases while increasing H₂
 - Energy transferred to the load is maintained when replacing NG with H₂
 - Non-monotonic NO_x emissions trend under progressive H₂ replacement
- **First CFD simulation performed of the dual-flame burner in the R&D pilot**
 - Satisfactory agreement is obtained between experiments and predicted temperatures ahead of the pile
 - Model refinement required prior to scaling up the burner to higher thermal power
- **Dual-flame burner qualified**
 - Fully compatible with neat natural gas, neat hydrogen, or any blend ratio
 - Offers adjustable thermal power split and fuel momentum
- **Successful industrial furnace trials at Imerys site (May 2025)**

Thank you
Any questions?